

**Sub-Nanometer Local Temperature Probing and Remotely Controlled Drug Release Based
on Azo-Functionalized Iron Oxide Nanoparticles**

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Abstract:

Local heating can be produced by iron oxide nanoparticles (IONPs) when exposed to an alternating magnetic field (AMF). To measure the temperature profile at the nanoparticle surface with a sub-nanometer resolution, here we present a molecular temperature-probe based on the thermal decomposition of a thermo-sensitive molecule, namely Azobis[*N*-(2-carboxyethyl)-2-methylpropionamidine]. Fluoresceineamine (FA) was bound to the azo molecule at the IONP surface *via* polyethylene glycol (PEG) spacers of different molecular weights. Significant local heating, with a temperature increase up to 45 K, was found at distances below 0.5nm from the surface of the nanoparticle, which decays exponentially with increasing distance. Furthermore, the temperature increase was found to scale linearly with the applied field at all distances. We implemented these findings in AMF-triggered drug release system in which doxorubicin was covalently linked at different distances from the IONP surface bearing the same thermo-labile azo molecule. We demonstrated the AMF triggered distance dependent release of the drug in a cytotoxicity assay on KB cancer cells.

Magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs) can be used as heat mediators to treat tumor tissues in the so-called magnetic induced hyperthermia therapy^{1,2,3,4,5,6}. To reach therapeutic temperature (42°C) at the targeted site, concentrations of several grams per liter of magnetic material have to be present in a confined volume^{7,8} which is not suitable when tumors are not easily reachable⁹. MNPs have been also proposed as drug carriers with remote release actuation operated by the heat generated by the nanoparticle upon exposure to an AMF^{10,11}. Recently, it was shown that even if the MNP concentration at the tumor cells did not produce macroscopic heating, MNPs could induce the apoptosis of tumor cells under AMF.^{2,12} Besides, it has been generally assumed that significant heating occurs only locally, that is, in the very close vicinity of the MNP surface¹³. The absence of a macroscopic temperature increase may reduce collateral effects arising from heating of healthy tissues.

To date, it is still challenging to quantify the local temperature profile for MNPs excited *via* an AMF. Classical methods for heat characterization (e.g. Specific Absorption Rate (SAR) measurements) are not suitable for measuring localized effects: i) the experiments have to be performed with highly concentrated dispersions of MNPs, where macroscopic heating of the environment occurs and inter-particle interactions cannot be excluded; ii) the SAR definition is only valid when the experiments are done in nearly adiabatic conditions, which are far from the conditions for a diluted solution where heat losses are dominant and hence the system is isothermal; and iii) the temperature recorded corresponds to the macroscopic temperature in the medium in which the MNPs are dispersed rather than the temperature at the nanoparticle surface.

Temperature mapping strategies were recently developed to measure the temperature at the nanoparticle surface.^{14,15} Jacobsen et al. reported a temperature molecular method based on the dehybridization of double strand DNAs bound to gold nanoparticles occurring under the application of a radio frequency field¹⁶. This effect was attributed to the local heating of gold nanoparticles induced by eddy currents¹⁷. More recently, Pralle et al. developed a similar strategy in which local temperature differences (ΔT) were measured using the temperature dependence fluorescence of the Dylight549 fluorophore conjugated to streptavidin-coated

magnetic nanoparticles. At elevated temperature, the decrease of the fluorescence intensities of Dylight549 with respect to that of a stable signal of the reference dye, the green fluorescent protein, in the cells allowed for ratiometric ΔT measurements. Furthermore, the authors could also monitor the effect of the local temperature increase by looking at the thermally activated TRPV1 ion channels, present at the cell surface, thus allowing the influx of calcium ions whenever local temperature reaches about 40°C. In both approaches, either the DNA melting temperature or the temperature sensitive proteins on living cells provided proofs of a local heating increase, but they could not probe the absolute temperatures achieved. Indeed the development of new molecular thermometer to probe the local temperature in cells has attracted much attention in the last years¹⁸. Uchiyama and coworkers¹⁴ developed a fluorescent polymeric thermometer capable to probe the absolute temperature inside cells. On the other hand, all methods so far applied for local temperature measurements lack spatial information and therefore no mapping of the temperature gradients at nanoparticles exposed to AMF have been reported. This information indeed plays a key role for the prediction of heat effect of magnetic nanoparticles induced by AMF and for the design of new therapeutic probes.

To measure the local temperature changes with spatial resolution on IONPs, when exposed to an AMF, we have here designed a fluorescent probe thermometer system which exhibits the following characteristics: i) it works with highly diluted solutions (5 nM particles concentration), where inter-particle interactions are minimized and isothermal conditions are ensured; ii) it measures at distinct distances from the nanoparticle surface in order to map the temperature gradient by linking a dye-thermo-labile group through different macromolecular spacers (PEG) to the IONPs, and iii) it measures over a long time lapse (1h) in order to measure the difference between global and local temperature in an equilibrium state.

In our approach, the FA dye attached to a thermo labile azo linker (2,2'-Azobis[*N*-(2-carboxyethyl)-2-methylpropionamide]) is bound to the particle surface through PEG spacers of distinct molecular weight and the dye release is monitored by photoluminescence. In this setup the IONPs are the heat mediators, the azo group is the thermometer, the FA allows for the optical read-out of the absolute temperature while the

PEG linker provides the spacer, thus allowing sub-nanometer spatial resolution of the temperature measurement.

Finally, herein, the temperature stimulation concept was extended for demonstrating controlled drug delivery. FA was replaced with a chemotherapeutic agent doxorubicin (DOX) in the same nanoparticle arrangement, under actuation by AMF control over the release rate of DOX was achieved and proven *in vitro* for KB cancer cells treatment.

We exploit the thermo labile molecule named Azobis[*N*-(2-carboxyethyl)-2-methylpropionamide] containing the azo group to measure upon excitation with AMFs ($f=334.5$ kHz, 9-17 mT) the local temperature increase of monodisperse superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles of 15 nm in diameter. The magnetic characterization of as synthesized IONPs indicated a blocking temperature of 238 K, a saturation magnetization of 40 emu/g, a strong exchange bias interaction of 275 Oe together with a large coercive field of 2225 Oe (see supporting information (SI), Figure S3). FA bound to the azo molecule was used as detection unit for monitoring the thermal decomposition degree of the azo group covalently linked to the IONP surface, by measuring the photoluminescence spectra of the solution (see Figure 1). To vary the distance between the azo molecule and the nanoparticle surface, the azo molecules were attached to the nanoparticles through PEG spacers of different molecular weights. The amount of dye molecules released from the IONPs, at fixed time laps, is directly correlated to the decomposition degree of the azo group which itself depends on the (local) temperature (T_{local}) at the IONP surface (for this specific azo molecule the 10h half life temperature in water is 57°C as stated by the supplier). Under AMF, the effective local heating can be expressed as the difference ΔT between the local temperature T_{local} and the global temperature T_{global} .

$$\Delta T = T_{local} - T_{global} \quad (1)$$

The global temperature is the temperature of the medium which surrounds the IONPs far away from their surface and can be measured with a temperature probe dipped into the solution.

Figure 1: Principle of ΔT measurements and used building blocks.

For the IONP-PEG-azo-FA the local temperature can be obtained based on the decomposition rate of the azo group (see Figure 1). To obtain the quantitative correlation between released FA and the local temperature, calibration curves were recorded at different temperatures and fixed time laps. For these experiments, three stable colloidal solutions of IONP-PEG-azo-FA ($M_w(\text{PEG})=500, 1500$ and 8000 Da) at 5 nM particles concentration in sodium borate buffer (pH 9, SBB9) were prepared and incubated for one hour at different temperatures, ranging from 20 - 80°C . Incubation in a water bath ensures the same temperature over the entire sample, being in this case the global temperature equal to the local temperature. The released dye was quickly separated from the IONPs by centrifugation in a membrane filter (molecular cut-off = 100 kDa) and the PL spectra of the downstreams recorded. The PL signal ($I_{\text{max, incubation}}$) increases with increasing temperature (see Figure 2b). In order to normalize the PL maxima at 510 nm, the three

samples at 5 nM particles concentration ($M_w(\text{PEG})=500, 1500$ and 8000 Da) were incubated at 80°C for 48h and the released dye (100% release) was separated from the IONPs by centrifugal filtration. The PL spectra of the downstreams were recorded and $I_{\text{max, incubation}}$ was normalized to $I_{\text{max, }80^\circ\text{C}, 48\text{h}}$.

Figure 2: Calibration curves.

The normalized PL intensities ($I_{\text{max}}=I_{\text{max, incubation}}/I_{\text{max, }80^\circ\text{C}, 48\text{h}}*100$) which represent the percentage of dye release, were plotted as a function of the incubation temperature and the data points fitted to an exponential function: $I_{\text{max}} = A \cdot e^{\left(\frac{T}{\tau}\right)}$ (T = incubation temperature; τ = decay rate; see Figure 2c). Comparable fitting parameters A and t for the three different samples were found. This indicates that the decomposition rate of the azo group is not independent on the spacer molecule and its molecular weight. Having these calibration

curves and by measuring the normalized PL intensity at 510 nm for samples exposed to an AMF, the local temperature at distinct distances from the nanoparticle surface can be extrapolated by using the following expression:

$$T_{local} = \ln\left(\frac{I_{max}}{A}\right) \cdot t \quad (2)$$

Samples of IONP-PEG-azo-FA ($M_w(\text{PEG}) = 500, 1500, \text{ and } 8000 \text{ Da}$) at 5 nM particles concentration were placed in a hyperthermia device (magneTherm® AC system Nanotherics Corp.). The solution temperature (T_{global}) was probed by placing an optical fiber into the sample solution and the temperature stayed constant over the entire measurement ($\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 hour). The magnetic field amplitude B can be tuned by changing the applied voltage on the coil. Magnetic field amplitudes spanning 9-17 mT ($7\text{-}13.5 \text{ kAm}^{-1}$) at 334.5 kHz were applied for 1h and the released dye quickly was separated from the particles by centrifugation in a centrifuge filter (MWCO 100 kDa). The PL spectra of the downstreams were recorded and the resulting $I_{max, AMF}$ were normalized ($I_{AFM} = I_{max, AFM} / I_{max, 80^\circ\text{C}, 48h} * 100$). With equations (1) and (2) and knowing the T_{global} , the difference between the local and the global temperature ΔT was calculated. In Figure 3a the ΔT values as a function of the applied magnetic field are reported for the three samples at different molecular weights of PEG. Significant ΔT values up to 45 K can be reached if the azo-FA group is linked through a very short spacer (500 Da PEG) to the IONP and the highest magnetic field amplitude (17 mT) is applied. On the contrary, longer PEG spacers lead to ΔT values around 10 K for the same magnetic field amplitude. Two clear trends can be observed: ΔT linearly increases with increasing magnetic field amplitude B and decreases exponentially with increasing molecular weight of the PEG spacer. This leads to the conclusion that ΔT is a function of the applied magnetic field amplitude (at a given frequency) and of the molecular weight of the PEG spacer (while the latter one represents the predominant effect due to exponential rather than a linear correlation between ΔT and distance). In a control experiment we exposed ultrasmall IONPs (6 nm in size) with Gallo1-1500kDaPEG-azo-FA and repeated the AMF experiments (see SI Figure S2). These particles have been shown to develop no local temperature increase.¹⁹ Indeed we obtained ΔT values

below 5K for these ultrasmall IONPs. This experiment clearly proves two points: i) the local temperature change and not the magnetic field itself induces the thermal decomposition of the azo link ii) the intrinsic properties of the IONP are crucial for efficient local heat generation.

Figure 3: ΔT results of the AMF experiments

In Figure 3b, ΔT is plotted versus B , showing for all PEG spacers a linear dependence with B . Depending on the molecular weight, the slope of the linear fit varies: higher molecular weights result in lower slopes, which can be explained by the different distance of the azo-FA end group to the excited IONP: The closer the thermo labile group is to the infinite cooling source (the aqueous solution) and thus the farther is the azo group from the nanoparticle surface, the less significant is the increase in local temperature with increasing fields. It should be pointed out that one expects that ΔT follows a power law with B as the SAR does for superparamagnetic nanocrystals.²⁰ This deviation may be attributed to the assumption of adiabatic conditions during a typical SAR determination experiment, which are far from the conditions used in our experiments. In diluted conditions and for excitation over long periods the system reaches an equilibrium state where both the global and the local temperature stay constant over time. The medium in which the IONPs are dispersed serves as an infinite cooling source and the heat flux from the IONPs surface stays constant. We can conclude from our experiments that under isothermal, equilibrium condition the increase in temperature on the IONPs surface scales linearly with the applied magnetic field.

To obtain the field dependent heat gradients, the molecular weight of PEG can be used to calculate the average distance of the azo-FA end group to the surface. In a random polymeric coil, the radius of gyration R_G is given by the following expression:

$$R_G = l \cdot \sqrt{\frac{M_w}{6 \cdot M_{monomer}}} \quad (3)$$

where l is the length of one monomer unit, M_w the molecular weight of the polymer and $M_{monomer}$ the molecular weight of the monomer. R_G is proportional to the square root of M_w , which means that low molecular weight polymers are present in a more stretched conformation than higher molecular weight polymers. In the case of PEG, l is equal to 0.35 nm, and $M_{monomer}$ is 44.05 g·mol⁻¹ and the resulting R_G values are summarized in Table S3. In a random coil the end group is located on average in the middle of the coil, which means that the azo-FA end group is at a distance from the IONP surface equal to R_G ²¹. In Figure 3c, ΔT is plotted versus the distance to the surface of the azo-FA end group (R_G), showing steep exponential decays of ΔT with increasing distance from the surface for all applied magnetic field amplitudes. For those IONPs, significant local temperature differences can be found in the range from 0 to 3 nm. The data points are numerically fitted with exponential decay functions of the type $\Delta T = A \cdot e^{-\left(\frac{d}{\tau}\right)}$, where d is the distance of the end group to the surface (see SI, Table S4b for fitting parameters). The difference between local and global temperature at the surface ($d=0$ nm) can be obtained by extrapolation of the fitting functions to $d \rightarrow 0$ resulting in $\Delta T = A$. At the surface, the absolute temperature is $T_{abs} = \Delta T_{d=0} + T_{global}$ (see SI, Table S5). At the highest field amplitude applied (17 mT), absolute temperatures around the boiling point of water were reached. Additionally, these data also demonstrate that under AMF and in diluted conditions the heat generated at the IONP surface is quite significant, however it is limited to the immediate proximity of the nanoparticle surface. The fast temperature decay profile support also recently reported results in which ion channels in neurons or plasma glucose can be remotely regulated by magnetic nanoparticles exposure to AMF.^{22,23} In analogy to our study, also in those studies the macroscopic temperature was kept well below the activation of the biological effects, thus suggesting that the effects were due to higher temperature

reached only locally at the cell membrane. We found also that the local heating effects are not significantly influenced by the concentration of the NPs within a defined range. Indeed we found the same release percentage, and hence ΔT values, when we used 10 times higher nanoparticle concentrations. At concentration below 2 nM the detection limit of the fluorophore FA is reached. For the design and application of AMF triggered drug release systems as well as for fundamental physical studies these results are of paramount significance.

Our findings can be indeed directly implemented in an AMF triggered drug release system if the fluorescent dye FA is replaced by Doxorubicine (DOX). Control over the DOX release rate could be achieved by positioning the thermo labile group at distinct distances from the IONPs, which results in different maximum ΔT values when the AMF is applied. To this end we synthesized IONP-PEG-azo-DOX compounds using PEG spacers at two different molecular weights (500 and 8000 Da, see Figure 4a).

Figure 4: Toxicity experiments.

The two IONP samples at distinct PEG molecular weight were dispersed in cold cell culture medium and each of them split in 3 aliquots. The first aliquot was centrifuged directly after the preparation in order to

precipitate the IONPs and the supernatants were collected and served as blanks (T_0 , no DOX release should be expected). One aliquot was incubated at room temperature (T_{RT}) for one hour and never exposed to AMF before centrifugation and collection of the supernatant. These samples provided the control for the release due to the thermal decomposition of the azo at RT (the temperature of the medium was equal to RT during the entire AFM treatment). For both IONP samples at distinct PEG molecular weights, about 12% of DOX was released at RT which is ascribed to the thermal decomposition of the azo. The third aliquot of each sample was treated for 1h at 334.5 kHz and 17 mT (T_{hyp}). The amount of DOX released via hyperthermia does depend on the local temperature on the IONPs surface during the AMF treatment. In fact, for the shorter PEG (500 Da), about 36% of DOX was released from the IONPs while for the compound bearing the longer PEG spacers (8000 Da) only 15% of DOX was released. These results are in good agreement with the experiments with FA and lead to the conclusion that neither the suspension media, nor the IONP concentration or the different molecules (DOX instead of FA) bound to the azo end group affect the decomposition rate of the azo group.

For cell toxicity experiments, supernatants (T_0 , T_{RT} and T_{hyp} containing different amount of DOX released from the nanoparticles) were used to treat KB cells for 6, 12 and 24h and the cytotoxicity effects was measured with a viability assay (PrestoBlue™ Reagent, Invitrogen). The fluorescence signals at 590 nm recorded before (as blank) and after the addition of the PrestoBlue reagent allowed to read the number of living cells for each sample. Upon AMF treatment, the IONP-500DaPEG-Azo-DOX released significant amount of DOX with respect to control samples at T_0 and at T_{RT} (see Figure 4b and c), while the 8000 Da PEG conjugate did not. Hence, the cytotoxicity of the sample with the short spacer was 3 times higher than that of the sample bearing the longer spacer. This clearly demonstrates the remarkable distance dependence of thermally induced decomposition of the azo group, the linker between the drug and the PEGylated IONP.

Finally, a further proof of the heat generated by the IONPs under AMF came from the comparison of magnetic characterization of the nanoparticles before and after exposure to AMF or to a heat annealing process (see SI, Figure S3). By recording the hysteresis curves, a remarkable improvement of the magnetic

properties (i.e. lower coercive fields and higher saturation magnetization) was observed for those samples exposed to AMF or heat with respect to the as-prepared nanocrystals which did not experience any local heating. As no macroscopic heating was observed during the AMF experiment, this leads to the conclusion that the improved magnetic features could be explained only if the nanoparticles had produced local heating.

In this work, thermo-labile azo-ligands anchored to superparamagnetic nanoparticles *via* PEG spacers can be utilized for: i) spatially resolved measurement of temperature surface profile on dilute solutions of iron oxide nanoparticles exposed to an AMF and ii) as linker between the cytostatic drug doxorubicin and a PEGylated iron oxide nanoparticle for AMF triggered drug release. By varying the molecular weight of the PEG spacer, the distance between the IONPs surface and the azo group can be tuned and thus the local temperature as a function of the distance to the nanoparticle surface could be assessed. Upon excitation with an AMF, the local nanoparticle temperature decays rapidly with increasing distance. Furthermore, we found that ΔT scales linearly with the applied fields for all molecular weights of the PEG under isothermal conditions. Also, in the drug release experiment, this carrier shows the following promising features as smart drug delivery systems: i) the mass ratio between the delivery vehicle and the drug is significantly reduced; ii) hydrophobic as well as hydrophilic drugs can be bound; iii) the drug release rate can be adjusted based on molecular building blocks (*i.e.* the azo molecules); and iv) combinations of different drugs bound on the same nanoparticle at different distances would enable independent release of each of them. The work here presented not only gives access to a new type of temperature sensors at the nanoscale for measuring the surface temperature gradient of magnetic nanocrystals under AMF exposure, but will allow for remotely triggering of combinatorial drug delivery in which more than one drug can be released using different kinetics and without any macroscopic heating, thus avoiding collateral effects to the surrounding tissues in proximity of tumors.

Materials and Methods

Azobis[*N*-(2-carboxyethyl)-2-methylpropionamidine]hydrate (VA057) was purchased from Wako Chemicals and all other chemicals were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and used as received. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker DRX 400 spectrometer. For the determination of iron concentration, Inductively Coupled Plasma Atomic Emission Spectroscopy (ICP-AES, ThermoFisher, CAP 6000) was utilized. Samples for ICP-AES were prepared by incubating 25 μL of sample overnight in 2 mL of aqua regia, and finally milliQ water was added to get a final volume of 25 mL. TEM images were obtained by a JEOL 1011 microscope operated at an accelerating voltage of 100 kV. TEM samples were prepared by drop-casting the solution on a carbon-coated copper grid and letting the solvent evaporate. For purification of the IONPs from free reagents after the synthesis, Amicon centrifuge filters (15 mL, 100 kDa molecular weight cut-off (MWCO), Millipore) were used in a temperature controlled centrifuge (Sigma, 3-16PK). For ultrapure samples, free FA or DOX was removed by two times gel filtration on PD10 desalting columns (GE Healthcare) with ice cold milliQ water as eluent. Incubation experiments were done in a temperature-controlled water bath (Mettler). Application of AMF to the samples was carried out in a magneTherm® AC device (Nanotherics Corp.). Separation of release FA from the particles was achieved by centrifugal filtration in Amicon tubes (0.5 mL, 100 kDa MWCO, Millipore) in a fixed angle, temperature-controlled centrifuge (Hettich, Mikro 200R). Fluorescence spectra were recorded on a Cary Eclipse Photospectrometer (Varian) in quartz 3-window micro-cuvettes (Hellma).

Synthesis of IONPs

Monodisperse IONPs with 15 nm core diameter were synthesized after a published procedure.²⁴ Briefly, 180 mg (2 mmol) of Fe₂O₃ hydrate (catalyst grade, 30-50 mesh), 2.82 g (10 mmol) of oleic acid (technical grade) and 5 g of octadecene were mixed in a 50 mL 3-neck flask equipped with a chiller and a N₂/vacuum inlet. The mixture was degassed under high vacuum and magnetic stirring for 1h and afterwards heated under N₂ atmosphere to 320°C for 1h. After cooling to room temperature, the nanoparticles were

precipitated 2 times with isopropanol (5:1 V/V) and one more time with acetone (5:1 V/V) at 3000 rpm/5min. The iron concentration was determined by ICP-AES and the core diameter by TEM.

Synthesis of GA-PEG

To a solution of 500 μmol Poly(ethylene glycol) (PEG) ($M_w = 500, 1500$ or 8000 g/mol) dissolved in 100 mL anhydrous tetrahydrofuran (THF) in a 3-neck flask, solutions of 500 μmol (85 mg) gallic acid (GA) dissolved in 50 mL THF and 50 μmol (6 mg) 4-Dimethylaminopyridine (DMAP) dissolved in 10 mL THF were added under magnetic stirring. The flask was equipped with a N_2 /vacuum inlet and a dropping funnel containing a solution of 2.5 mmol (520 mg) *N,N'*-Dicyclohexylcarbodiimide (DCC) which was added dropwise within 1h to the PEG/GA/DMAP solution. After stirring for 16h under N_2 atmosphere, THF was removed under reduced pressure, yielding crude yellowish gallol-PEG (GA-PEG) as a waxy solid. GA-PEG was dissolved in 100 mL milliQ water at 40°C within 1h and the pH as adjusted with 0.1 M HCl to pH 2 to crystallize the hydrolyzed DCC which could be filtered off with a paper filter. In a 500 mL separating funnel, GA-PEG was extracted three times from the aqueous phase with chloroform. The solvent was removed from the combined organic phase under reduced pressure at 60°C yielding GA-PEG as a yellow waxy solid. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta(\text{ppm}) = 6.98$ (Ar-H), 4.64 (CH_2 -ester), 3.62-3.28 (CH_2 , OH-PEG).

Ligand exchange and water transfer

Oleic acid capped IONPs in toluene (1 volume equivalent, $c_{\text{Fe}} = 10$ g/L) were mixed with a GA-PEG solution (1 volume equivalent, 0.1M in CHCl_3) in a separating funnel. Triethylamine was added (0.05 volume equivalents) and the mixture was diluted with ca. 5 volume eq. of toluene. MilliQ water (5 volume equivalents) was added and the two phases were allowed to emulsify by gentle shaking. In this stage the ligand-exchange occurred and the IONPs tended to segregate at the toluene-water interface. Acetone was added (ca. 10 volume eq.) in order to destabilize the particles in the organic phase (toluene/chloroform/acetone) and drive them quantitatively into the aqueous phase. The mixture was shaken

again gently up to emulsification. After phase separation, the aqueous phase was collected. This step was repeated three times. Residual organic solvents (acetone, toluene) were removed stepwise from the combined aqueous phases under reduced pressure (300mbar/40°C/30min, 200mbar/40°C/30min, 77mbar/40°C/30min). For purification, the aqueous solution containing the IONP-PEG-OH was diluted with milliQ water and re-concentrated in centrifuge filters (MWCO 100 kDa, 3000rpm). This step was repeated at least five times. Finally the iron concentration was determined by ICP-AES.

Synthesis of IONP-PEG-azo-COOH

To a ice cold aqueous colloidal solution of IONP-PEG-OH (2 mL, $c_{Fe} = 10$ g/L) a solution of 25 mg Azobis[*N*-(2-carboxyethyl)-2-methylpropionamidine]hydrate (VA057) dissolved in 10 mL ice cold milliQ water was added and shaken at 6°C. 10 mL of a freshly prepared, ice cold aqueous solution containing 10 mg 1-Ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)carbodiimide (EDC) and 3 mg DMAP was added to the VA057 solution and the mixture was shaken over 16h at 6°C. For purification of IONP-PEG-azo-COOH the solution was diluted with ice cold milliQ water and re-concentrated 5 times in centrifuge filters (MWCO 100 kDa, 3000rpm) in a temperature-controlled centrifuge at 6°C. The samples were stored at 6°C and the iron concentration was determined by ICP-AES.

Synthesis of IONP-PEG-azo-FA or IONP-PEG-azo-DOX

Fluoresceinamine (FA, isomer I, 5 mg,) or doxorubicine (DOX, 2.5 mg) was dissolved in 10 mL THF and was added to an aqueous solution containing IONP-PEG-azo-COOH (2 mL, $c_{Fe} = 10$ g/L), 25 mg EDC and 25 mg *N*-Hydroxysuccinimid (NHS). The mixture was shaken for 20 min at room temperature and then rapidly cooled by placing the vial in an ice bath. THF was removed from the ice cold solution with nitrogen flux and the final product IONP-PEG-azo-FA/DOX was purified five times by dilution with ice cold milliQ water and re-concentration in centrifuge filters (15 mL, MWCO 100 kDa, 3000 rpm) in a centrifuge at 6°C. To remove the last traces of unbound FA/DOX, the concentrated samples were passed two times through a

G25 Sephadex gel filtration column at 6°C. The samples were stored at 6°C and iron concentrations were determined by ICP-AES.

Incubation experiments

Colloidal solutions of IONP-PEG-azo-FA ($M_w(\text{PEG}) = 500, 1500 \text{ or } 8000 \text{ Da}$) were diluted in ice cold sodium borate buffer (pH 9, SBB9) to reach a final concentration of $c_{\text{NP}} = 5 \text{ nM}$. These stock solutions were used for the incubation and the AMF experiments. 0.5 mL aliquots were filled into 1.5 mL disposable Eppendorf vials. For each incubation temperature, 3 individual aliquots were placed in a temperature-controlled water bath for 1h. After the time lapsed, the solutions were filled into Amicon centrifuge filters (0.5 mL, 100 kDa MWCO) and centrifuged for 5 min at 14000 rpm. In this step the released FA is washed down the filter while the IONPs are blocked by the cellulose acetate membrane. To recover FA molecules eventually trapped in the filters, 0.5 mL ice cold SBB9 was added to the dry filter and centrifuged again for 5 min at 14000 rpm. The downstreams were collected and stored in the dark before they were analyzed by fluorescence spectroscopy.

AMF experiments

An aliquot of IONP-PEG-azo-FA ($M_w(\text{PEG}) = 500, 1500 \text{ or } 8000 \text{ Da}$) at $c_{\text{NP}} = 5 \text{ nM}$ in SBB9 was placed in the middle of the coil in the Magnetherm device. An optical thermoprobe was dipped in the solution to measure online the macroscopic temperature which was constant over the entire measurement and equal to the room temperature. Fields of $B = 9, 13 \text{ or } 17 \text{ mT}$ were applied for 1h and after the time lapsed, the solutions were filled into Amicon centrifuge filters (0.5 mL, 100 kDa MWCO) and centrifuged 5 min at 14000 rpm. The released FA is washed down the filter while the IONPs are blocked by the cellulose acetate membrane. To recover FA molecules eventually trapped in the filters, 0.5 mL ice cold SBB9 was added to the dry filter and centrifuged again for 5 min at 14000 rpm.

For each sample with different molecular weight of PEG and each field B this procedure was repeated 2 times in order to triplicate the results. The downstreams were collected and stored in the dark before they were analyzed by fluorescence spectroscopy.

Fluorescence spectroscopy

The downstreams of the incubation and AMF experiments were analyzed by fluorescence spectroscopy. Note that all samples (I_{max} , $I_{max, AMF}$, $I_{max, 80^{\circ}C, 48h}$) were recorded on the same day in order to avoid fluctuations of the maximum intensity due to the lamp. The instrument was switched on 1h before the measurement in order to stabilize the lamps temperature. Samples were measured in 3-window quartz micro-cuvettes by excitation at 460 nm (slits 5 nm/5 nm, U(detector) = 600 V). The emission signals were collected from 495-650 nm.

Determination of DOX concentration

Samples of IONP-PEG-azo-DOX ($M_w(\text{PEG}) = 500$ or 8000 Da) dispersed in cell culture media (RPMI with 10% FBS) were incubated for 48h at 80°C followed by centrifugation at 14000 rpm for 10 min to precipitate the IONPs leaving the released DOX (100%) in solution. The supernatants were collected and analyzed by fluorescence spectroscopy. The concentration was calculated by a calibration function obtained by measuring the PL intensity at 550 nm (excitation 460 nm) of a DOX dilution series (supporting information, Figure S1). By dividing the DOX concentration by the particles concentration, the number of DOX molecules per IONP could be calculated to be 319 DOX/IONP for the IONPs bearing 500 Da PEG and 135 DOX/IONP for the NPs bearing 8000 Da PEG spacers.

Cell experiments

For the cell viability experiments, both IONP-PEG-azo-DOX samples (500 and 8000 Da) were adjusted to a final maximum DOX concentration of 5.5 ug/mL ($C_{\text{NP-500PEG-azo-DOX}} = 0.42 \mu\text{M}$ and $C_{\text{NP-8000PEG-azo-DOX}} = 0.92 \mu\text{M}$) with 6°C cell culture medium (RPMI with 10% FBS). The viability assay was performed

using the PrestoBlue™ Cell Viability Reagent (Invitrogen). Briefly, $2 \cdot 10^4$ KB cells suspended in 0.2 mL of serum supplemented medium were seeded in a 96 multiwell plate and allowed to grow for 24h at 37°C and 5% of CO₂. Dispersions of IONPs-PEG-azo-DOX ($M_w(\text{PEG}) = 500$ or 8000 Da) in cell culture medium were centrifuged for 10 min at 14000 rpm just after the preparation (T_0), after 1h at room temperature (T_{RT}) and after 1h AMF treatment at 334.5 kHz, 17 mT (T_{AMF}). The supernatants (containing different amount of DOX released from the nanoparticles) were used to treat the cells for 6, 12 and 24 h, then the medium was removed, the cells were washed with PBS and fresh medium was added. The fluorescence signals at 590 nm were analyzed by TECAN plate reader before (as blank) and after the addition of the PrestoBlue cell viability reagent for 30 min. Each assay was repeated 3 times and the cytotoxicity values of the supernatants after the AMF treatment T_{AMF} were compared both to the cytotoxicity values of the control at T_0 and at T_{RT} .

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Author Contributions:

A.R., P.G., A.C. and T.P. are responsible for the study concept and design. A.R, A.C. and P.G. carried out the experiments. A.R., P.G., T.P., M.A.G., R.C. and L.M have analyzed the data. All authors have contributed to the writing of the manuscript.

Financial Interests statement:

The authors declare no competing financial interests. Supplementary information accompanies this paper at www.nature.com/naturenanotechnology. Reprints and permission information is available online at <http://www.nature.com/reprints>. Correspondence and requests for materials should be addressed to T.P.

Figure Legends:

Figure 1: Principle of ΔT measurements and used building blocks. a) Sketch of the local-to-global temperature differences measurement principle in a hyperthermia device. A fluorescence dye linked to the IONPs through azo-PEG spacer groups decomposes as a function of temperature and time and the dye release enables local temperature measurements. Global temperatures are assessed by an optical temperature probe. b) Building blocks of the local temperature probe. 15 nm spherical IONPs (scalebar 50 nm) are functionalized stepwise with gallo1-PEG ($M_w=500, 1500$ or 8000 Da), an azo-molecule (VA057) and fluoresceine amine (FA).

Figure 2: Calibration curves. a) Sketch of the readily functionalized IONPs bearing FA connected through VA057 azo molecule to the tails of PEG spacers of different molecular weights. Increase in temperature results in increased cleavage of the azo group and release of the dye from the particles. The released FA is separated from the nanoparticles by centrifugation and the PL spectra of the downstreams are recorded. b) Calibration curves. Samples of IONP-PEG-azo-FA (5 nM) were incubated for 1h at temperature from 20 to 80°C , Released FA was separated and the PL spectra were recorded. Intensities were normalized to the maximum release (IONP-PEG-azo-FA sample incubated for 48h at 80°C). c) Quantitative correlations between the PL of the downstreams are obtained by plotting the release versus the incubation temperature and by fitting the data point with exponential functions. The error bars display the SD.

Figure 3: Temperature profile gradients. a) ΔT values as functions of applied magnetic field amplitudes and $M_w(\text{PEG})$ after 1h of AMF treatment are plotted. ΔT decreases with decreasing field amplitudes and

increasing $M_w(\text{PEG})$. b) ΔT plotted as a function of field amplitude reveals linearly increasing values for all $M_w(\text{PEG})$. c) Temperature gradients for all field amplitudes: significant local-to-global temperature differences can be found at distances shorter than 3 nm.

Figure 4: Toxicity experiments. a) Sketch of the readily functionalized IONPs bearing DOX which is covalently linked through VA057 azo to the PEG spacers of different two different M_w (500 and 8000 Da). b) Cytotoxicity within 24h of DOX released from IONPs-500 Da PEG after AFM treatment compared to a sample incubated 1h at RT (T_{RT}) and to a blank kept for 1h at RT (T_0). c) Cytotoxicity of DOX released from IONPs-8000 Da PEG after AFM treatment compared to a sample incubated 1h at RT (T_{RT}) and to a blank (T_0).